

Can the Diagnosis and Support of Offenders with ADHD Help Reduce Reoffending?

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17112739 | ISSN: 2977-1676

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www.journalcjd.org

British Library Registered ISSN: 2977-1676

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17112739>

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Crime & Justice
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Abstract

The United Kingdom is currently facing a crisis with prison overcrowding and reoffending. This study looks at the connection between Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) and the rates of reoffending among offenders, focusing on ADHD's prevalence within the criminal justice system. It assesses how diagnosing and treating ADHD may impact re-offending, considering the diagnoses effects on offending behaviour. To answer this a literature review was conducted using a systematic approach which utilises a thematic analysis of existing literature, exploring themes related to ADHD offenders, including links to violent offences, the need for improved screening, and the influence of comorbid conditions. It finds that many imprisoned individuals with ADHD are undiagnosed, leading to inadequate support during and after imprisonment. Effective treatment strategies, such as medication and psychological support, are crucial for lowering reoffending rates. The results highlight the importance of implementing systematic ADHD screenings in the criminal justice system and underscore the necessity for tailored support post-release, suggesting that timely intervention could reduce reoffending and improve reintegration outcomes. This underscores the vital role of social work in addressing the specific needs of this vulnerable group, which is often overlooked in conventional rehabilitation programs, emphasising the need for a more informed approach.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

When deciding on the topic for my research proposal and dissertation, I knew early on that I wanted it to be in some way related to Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder, commonly referred to as ADHD, and the impacts it has on those diagnosed with the condition. As I considered the options for how I wanted to approach this, I began my final placement as a student social worker as part of an Adolescent team in Children's Services. This team worked to support young people who were often the victims of criminal exploitation. This exploitation resulted in many of the young people being arrested and charged with a variety of offences which included serious violent offences. As I spoke with professionals who supported these young people, they often spoke of the unmet needs which were a factor in the young person being at a higher risk of exploitation, with ADHD being mentioned repeatedly. After hearing this I decided to begin look to see what research had been done in relation to ADHD and individuals who were in some way involved in the criminal justice system.

1.2 What is Attention Deficit/Hyperactive Disorder (ADHD)?

Attention Deficit/Hyperactive Disorder (ADHD) is a lifelong neurodevelopmental disorder with three main groups of symptoms related to impulsivity, inattention and hyperactivity (Vold *et al.*, 2023). It is only relatively recently that ADHD has been recognised in adults, having previously only been believed to affect children; however, it is now thought that between 1-2% of adults in the United Kingdom have ADHD (McCarthy *et al.*, 2012). While each individual with ADHD's symptoms will present to an extent differently for each individual, symptoms linked to hyperactivity are believed to reduce to a degree as the child progresses into adulthood (McCarthy *et al.*, 2012). Adults diagnosed with ADHD tend to suffer to a greater degree with inability to maintain attention on tasks for long periods, Poor time management, and poor organisational skills. They are often forgetful (McCarthy *et al.*, 2012, p. 2). Other symptoms associated with ADHD include emotional dysregulation resulting in inappropriate expressions of emotion, angry outbursts and irritability (Anker, Ginsberg and Heir, 2021, p. 2).

1.3 Key Background of ADHD and the CJS

After deciding on a topic, I began my research to see if what research was available discussing the Impact of ADHD in relation to the criminal Justice system. I soon found a report commissioned in 2020 by the then Lord Chancellor for a review of evidence in relation to neurodiversity and the criminal justice system. The report stated that an estimated 1 to 2 per cent of the adult population in the United Kingdom has ADHD, but evidence indicated that neurodivergent individuals are overrepresented in the criminal justice system (Ministry of Justice, 2021). This report also highlighted specific concerns around

the ability of neurodivergent individuals to address offending behaviour to avoid reoffending, as well as the ability to comply with licence conditions after being released from prison, which would result in their recall to prison (Ministry of Justice, 2021). This report gave me the first indication that neurodivergent conditions such as ADHD were being noticed within the criminal justice system.

Continued research brought me to the ADHD Foundation, which is a charity based in the United Kingdom that supports and advocates for people living with ADHD. While on their website, I found a report which described ways individuals with ADHD can be supported in the criminal justice system. The report highlighted that an estimated 25% of offenders have ADHD and that prisoners with ADHD had much higher levels of aggression recorded than prisoners without ADHD (Takeda, 2022). It also stated the need for improvements to be made in screening prisoners for ADHD the report describes that the current process of screening is insufficient to accurately determine if a prisoner has ADHD (Takeda, 2022).

Additional evidence demonstrating the effects of ADHD in regards to the criminal justice system came from a study conducted on the driving behaviour of individuals diagnosed with ADHD. The study found drivers with ADHD were less likely to use mirrors and signalling while overtaking, while also more likely to be driving over the speed limit (Groom *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, the study suggested that individuals with ADHD had higher rates of road rage due to difficulties with regulating emotion, which could contribute to serious accidents (Groom *et al.*, 2015).

Further research produced by Professor Amanda Kirby on behalf of the HM Inspectorate of Probation, looking into Neurodiversity in relation to Youth offending, demonstrated that this didn't relate only to offending in adults. In this report, Professor Kirby concluded that one in three people going through the criminal justice system might be neurodivergent. It also found that rates of certain youth offending were much higher in relation to ADHD (Kirby, Amanada, 2021). After reading this, I continued my research and expanded to include any reports published outside of the UK relating to ADHD and offending.

These reports were not limited to only the United Kingdom. A study carried out in Norway looking into the prevalence of criminal convictions in adults with ADHD found that ADHD adults were involved in a higher number of criminal incidents (Anker, Ginsberg and Heir, 2021). This study also stated that the criminal incidents committed by people with ADHD seemed to be more opportunistic rather than planned, resulting in higher rates of convictions (Anker, Ginsberg and Heir, 2021). These higher rates of

criminal conviction were found to be for both men and women and were associated with emotional dysregulation and impulsivity (Anker, Ginsberg and Heir, 2021).

After reading these studies, I decided I wanted to approach this topic in a way that looked at ways in which offenders can be supported. Social workers will often work with offenders, for example, if the offender is under the age of 18 or other vulnerabilities are identified. When working with service users who are also offenders the social worker will aim to support in a number of ways to try and address offending behaviour. Depending on the individual, this could range from helping to identify education and employment opportunities to supporting the individual in programmes focused on substance misuse. In this setting, it has been suggested that individuals with ADHD have higher levels of offending behaviour (Anker, Ginsberg and Heir, 2021). With that in mind, I made the decision that my question would be “Can the diagnosis and treatment of offenders who have ADHD help to reduce reoffending rates?”

1.4 The Current Crisis

Currently the United Kingdom is facing a crisis with prison overcrowding with the lord Chancellor Shabana Mahmood saying in July 2024 telling members of parliament that the prison system was close to collapse. At the time, it was reported that 99% of prison cells were in use, and the remaining available cell space could run out in weeks (Ministry of Justice, 2024). To tackle this crisis, the government began a program that would make offenders of certain crimes eligible for release after serving 40% of their sentence (Ministry of Justice, 2024). Statistics released by the Ministry of Justice show that between July 2024 and September 2024, 14920 prisoners were released, with this number being 21% higher than the same period in 2023, with the release programs being the cause of this increase (Ministry of Justice, 2025).

These same statistics also show that 9975 prisoners were recalled to prison for breaching the conditions of their licence, with this being a 42% increase during the same period the year before (Ministry of Justice, 2025). While these statistics do not give details as to the nature of these breaches, it does help to highlight the high rates of reoffending in the criminal justice system. In 2020, the Ministry of Justice released a white paper titled A Smarter Approach to Sentencing, which described reoffending as one of the biggest challenges facing the criminal justice system. It was reported that in 2018 to 2019, 80% of those who were convicted or cautioned had already at least one previous caution or conviction (Ministry of Justice, 2020). With this in mind, diagnosing and treating offenders who have ADHD might

provide a way to reduce reoffending rates, given that they could make up a disproportionate percentage of the prison population.

Chapter 2: Methodology

This study will be looking at the question: Can the diagnosis and treatment of offenders who have ADHD help to reduce reoffending rates? I've carried out a literature review using a systematic approach to try to answer this question. This approach was chosen as I was unable to carry out a systematic literature review as outlined by the Cochrane or Campbell Collaboration, as this is considered to be beyond the scope of a student researcher (Aveyard 2014). To find the literature for this review, I used the London Metropolitan University online library E-resource catalogue. At the same time, trying to find suitable keywords which would provide me with relevant literature needed to complete the literature review. As part of this, I conducted a number of searches which helped me to narrow down my inclusion and exclusion criteria and helped me to determine that "ADHD and Criminal Justice" had to be included in the search to give me enough suitable materials for me to use. I found that I also needed to include "United Kingdom" as part of the search with the aim of reducing the number of results to a more manageable level, and also aim to keep the results focusing on a single criminal justice system.

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
-English -ADHD -Criminal Justice -United Kingdom	-Languages other than English -Other neurodiverse conditions -Settings outside of the criminal justice system.

Fig 1. Table of the inclusion and exclusion criteria

The first systematic search was conducted on 01/12/2024 using the London Metropolitan University Online Library E-resource catalogue. Using the advanced search option, I entered in ADHD Criminal Justice with the filters Full Text, Peer Reviewed, and available at London Met, all selected. This search yielded 226 results, but after reading through a number of abstracts within these results, I could see that a large number of them related to a number of different countries other than the United Kingdom. I conducted a further search using the London Metropolitan University Online Library E-resource

catalogue, entering “ADHD Criminal Justice United Kingdom”. This search yielded 22 results. To narrow this down further, I added an additional filter request that I only be shown literature published after 1/01/2010. This date was chosen as I wanted to see if there had been a change in the results and view of the impact of ADHD in regards to offending. This inclusion gave me 18 results. Within these results, five were removed as they were duplicating titles. I then read through the remaining 11 titles, after which a further seven articles were excluded, with the reasons outlined below. One article was removed as it focused on the strain ADHD services are under in the United Kingdom, but did not mention what impact ADHD has on offending, re-offending, or any other part of the criminal justice system. One article was excluded as it focused on the prevalence of mental ill health and unmet needs of people in police custody. While this article did have a small section discussing neurodiversity, it did not distinguish between different conditions and the effect they had on offending and re-offending. One article was removed as it focused on tools used to diagnose those in custody with ADHD and did not mention the effect the condition has on reoffending or possible options for treatment. One article was excluded as it only discussed the capability of young defendants to take part in criminal justice proceedings, with no link made to ADHD. One article was excluded as it was a special editorial and did not give the detailed information needed for my literature review. One article was excluded as it focused only on sexual assault offences and did not have a specific focus on ADHD in relation to these offences. Finally, 1 article was excluded as it had no relation to ADHD or the criminal justice system.

After going through this process, six articles were selected for analysis; these articles can be found. To do this, I chose to use Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis, which is a method for identifying, analysing and reporting themes within the literature in a rich level of detail (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Within this method, a theme is highlighted as something significant in the literature that relates to the research question (Braun and Clarke, 2006). To identify these themes, Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis is done through a six-stage process, which was followed as part of this literature review. This involves familiarising yourself with the literature, then highlighting and coding interesting points within the literature. These codes are then collected together to form potential themes within the literature set, which are then defined and named, which helps provide a clear pattern of findings, which will be shown in the following chapter (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Stage 1: Familiarize yourself with the literature.	Familiarize yourself with the literature by reading through multiple times and making notes of initial ideas.
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Stage 2: Coding interesting points	Highlighting and coding interesting points within the literature in a systematic way.
Stage 3: Searching for themes	Review this coding and begin to group them into potential themes.
Stage 4: Review themes	Cross reference these themes with the extracts gathered during the coding process to ensure there is the evidence to support the themes.
Stage 5: Defining and naming themes	Refine these themes to generate clear definitions and names for each theme.
Stage 6: Generating the report	Once the themes have been finalised begin writing up the report as part of the findings chapter.

Fig. 2. Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-stage process.

Chapter 3: Findings

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter, I will be exploring the key findings that emerged from completing the thematic analysis of the literature. These findings have been grouped into three themes: Violent offending, ADHD screening and treatment and finally, comorbidities and other challenges facing ADHD offenders.

3.2 Violent Offending

While conducting my analysis, the first thing that stood out was the references between ADHD and higher rates of violent offending. It should be noted that the articles themselves did not give a definitive list of what constituted a violent offence. However, the Crown Prosecution Service considers violent offences to cover crimes in relation to assault, robbery, knife offences, firearms offences, manslaughter and murder (The Crown Prosecution Service, 2025). This was a consistent theme found throughout research, with a study into the identification and management of ADHD offenders within the criminal justice system stating that ADHD was a significant predictor when looking at violent offending (Young *et al*, 2011). This is echoed in Román-Ithier *et al*'s (2017) study, which suggests that there is a direct link between ADHD and repeat violent offending. Young *et al*, (2011) research shows that this violent offending continued while incarcerated with individuals with ADHD symptoms recording eight times more aggressive incidents than other prisoners. This is also supported by Young and Thome, 2011 who found that incarcerated individuals with undiagnosed and untreated ADHD had a greater difficulty in managing the stresses of prison life and that these individuals recorded higher rates of aggressive incidents. This was believed to be related to a number of factors such as impulsive responding, mood instability and lower ability to tolerate frustrating situations, all of which are traits associated with ADHD (Young and Thome, 2011).

A study conducted looking into Neuro development disorders in prison inmates went on to suggest that possible explanation for offending outcomes of individuals with ADHD could be related to the higher rates of risk-taking behaviour and impulsivity leading to many being imprisoned due to offences linked to a lack of behaviour control with the majority of offences reactive or based on opportunity rather than pre planned (Young *et al*, 2018). This impulsivity and risk-taking behaviour could be seen as a contributing factor which would help explain the higher levels of aggressive incidents and violent offending linked to ADHD.

Additionally, Young and Thome's, 2011 study into ADHD and offenders found that individuals with ADHD received their first conviction at a much younger age, compared to individuals who did not show symptoms of ADHD. The study also noted that violent offences made up a large percentage of these convictions. This study also found that individuals with ADHD had a higher likelihood of reoffending than those without ADHD symptoms (Young and Thome, 2011). Román-Ithier et al's (2017) study, which aimed to examine prisoners who demonstrated ADHD symptoms in childhood, results support this. They found that there was a significant link in relation to individuals whose first arrest was before the age of 15, who often demonstrated ADHD symptoms in childhood. The results also showed that individuals who demonstrated ADHD symptoms in childhood were far more likely to be repeat offenders of both violent and non-violent crimes (Román-Ithier *et al.*, 2017).

The link between ADHD and higher rates of reoffending was also seen in Jane Wood's study, which looked at the experiences of ADHD individuals serving a community sentence and the probation officers supporting them. This study states that offenders with neurodevelopmental disorders such as ADHD have an increased risk of offending due to factors related to poor executive function, impulsivity, poor attainment and difficulties with personal organisation. Probation officers who took part in this study said that ADHD service users often needed extra support when it came to remembering to attend appointments and that allowances should be made; otherwise, these individuals could be at risk of breaching their court orders (Wood, 2024).

3.3 ADHD screening and treatment

The second theme highlighted during the analysis was the findings related to the screening of individuals with suspected ADHD who have been imprisoned or are serving a community sentence. This was something that was not highlighted as consistently in the articles; this could be because screening for ADHD was not the main aim of every article selected for analysis. However, when ADHD screening was mentioned, there was a consistent call for individuals to be screened soon after receiving a custodial sentence or community order. During a study conducted into the economic impact of ADHD in the Scottish prison system, they found that 80% of the inmates who took part in the study had no prior diagnosis for ADHD. This, according to Young et al (2018), would suggest that a significant percentage of the prison population is not receiving adequate support due to inadequate ADHD screening (Young *et al.*, 2018).

The need for improved ADHD screening is also recognised in Young et al (2011), who highlight the urgent need for improvement in the screening, assessment and treatment for individuals entering

prison. But also draws attention to the challenges in implementing this. One challenge is the need to carry out assessments and interventions quickly, as an estimated half of individuals spend six months or less in prison (Young *et al.*, 2011). With this in mind, Young et al (2011) suggests solutions such as the integrated treatment system, which could be an effective pathway for introducing ADHD assessment and management, which will include provisions for support to continue after the individual has left prison (Young *et al.*, 2011). The need for creative solutions to screen for ADHD has also been called for by probation services, who believe identifying and supporting their service users with ADHD could improve engagement with court orders and reduce breaches (Wood, 2024).

The articles that discussed the need for improved ADHD screening within the criminal justice system also highlighted that this was only the first step in trying to support ADHD offenders while in prison and to reduce reoffending upon their release. As part of this, once an individual has received a diagnosis, they are able to start receiving appropriate treatment and support. Within the United Kingdom, the National Institute for Clinical Excellence recommends that medication be used as a primary treatment for an individual who's been deemed to have severe ADHD (Young and Thome, 2011). Young et al (2011) state that treating ADHD prisoners using medication should always be considered as part of any support programme. The belief is that using medication will reduce ADHD symptoms, including emotional instability, impulsivity and inattentiveness, which negatively impact the behaviour within prison. With this reduction in ADHD symptoms, these individuals will be better able to take part in programs aimed at reducing the likelihood of reoffending once they have been released from prison. Finally, the treatment of an offender's ADHD while in prison could lead to improvements of other disorders commonly found in ADHD offenders, ranging from personality disorders, alcohol and substance misuse, along with other forms of addiction, and in mental health conditions such as anxiety and depression (Young *et al.*, 2011). Although medication is not thought to be the only option when treating and supporting individuals with ADHD, a study carried out in Sweden found that there was a decrease in criminality of 41% for women and 32% in men while they were being treated with medication (Young *et al.*, 2018).

While the analysis of the selected articles highlighted that medication can be used to support ADHD offenders in reducing criminality, medication alone might not be sufficient when treating more serious offenders with ADHD. With these offenders, a more complex intervention using both psychological treatment and medication is needed as the offending behaviour is not attributed solely to ADHD symptoms alone, as these individuals often have a range of different comorbidities that contribute to offending and reoffending (Young and Thome, 2011). As a result of this, the combined psychological

and medication treatment is believed to be needed, with the medication improving symptoms associated with ADHD, such as emotional dysregulation and impulsivity. In addition to this, psychological treatment is needed to tackle comorbidities that contribute to offending behaviour. An example is alcohol and substance dependence, which is often found in ADHD offenders (Young and Thome, 2011). This is something I will be expanding on further in as part of the final theme.

3.4 Comorbidities and challenges facing offenders with ADHD

The final theme that was discussed in some way repeatedly was that prisoners and those serving community sentences who were found to have ADHD overwhelmingly had other comorbidities that could be argued to be contributing to these individuals' offending and re-offending or negatively affecting their health and wellbeing. Within the prison population, mental health disorders are common, with adequate support often not available for those needing it. Progress has been made in some areas to help prisoners with acute mental health disorders, but this has not been the case with neurodevelopmental disorders such as ADHD (Young *et al.*, 2018). This is significant as it is common for individuals with ADHD to have comorbidities such as substance and alcohol abuse disorders, dyslexia, and personality disorder (Young *et al.*, 2011).

Young and Thome (2011) reported that an estimated 40-60% of young people with ADHD will develop a comorbid disorder, including a range of anti-social behavioural disorders. This, combined with ADHD, significantly increases the likelihood that these individuals will engage in anti-social or criminal behaviour (Young and Thome, 2011). This increase in anti-social and criminal behaviour increases the risk of ADHD individuals becoming involved with the criminal justice system and receiving prison sentences. Additionally, as part of a study into the economic consequences of ADHD in Scottish prisons, it was reported that an estimated 25% of prisoners were at substantial risk of having a psychiatric comorbidity and a much harder time adjusting to life in prison (Young *et al.*, 2018).

Young *et al.* (2018) also highlighted that prisoners with ADHD had a lower quality of life while in prison than those who did not have ADHD. They also found that prisoners with ADHD had poorer health scores in relation to vision and mobility, with the lower vision scores being linked to difficulties in reading. In regard to the lower levels of mobility, it is believed that this could be a result of ADHD prisoners suffering more injuries that would have a negative impact on their mobility. Data reported in Denmark supports this, as they found the morbidity rate was three times higher for Prisoners with ADHD, and 77% of deaths were reported in relation to accidental injury.

Chapter 4: Critical Discussion

4.1 Screening and Treatment

As highlighted in the findings chapter, the research indicates that there is a consistent association between individuals with ADHD and violent offending, with one study stating that ADHD was a predictor for violent offending (Young *et al*, 2011). This was something that came up consistently in the literature and has been attributed to emotional dysregulation, impulsivity and a low ability to tolerate frustrating situations (Young and Thome, 2011). This was also seen as part of a study into the identification and management of ADHD offenders within the criminal justice system, untreated ADHD individuals who were involved in eight times more aggressive incidents than other prisoners (Young *et al*, 2011).

These higher levels of aggression linked to traits associated with ADHD demonstrate the need to begin screening individuals for ADHD once they have been convicted of a crime. Beginning screening at this stage would be key, as it was found during a study into the economic consequences of ADHD in the Scottish prison system that 25.5 per cent of the population were found to have ADHD (Young *et al.*, 2018). This is a disproportionately large percentage given that it is estimated that between 1 and 2 per cent of adults in the United Kingdom have ADHD (Ministry of Justice, 2021). Additionally, it was found that 80% of these inmates did not have a diagnosis until the study was completed (Young *et al.*, 2018). These figures demonstrate that a sizable number of adult prisoners are not receiving the support needed while they are in custody.

Admittedly, there are clear challenges in introducing ADHD screening more effectively throughout the criminal justice system. It has been highlighted in the literature that these assessments would need to be completed in a short space of time due to many prisoners only serving sentences of six months or less (Young *et al.*, 2011). This has led to the call for creative solutions such as the integrated treatment that could prove to be effective in assessing and managing ADHD offenders as it includes provisions for support to continue after the individual has been released from prison which continue after they have been released. In this approach, social workers could take an active role in providing support once the offender is released from prison. Solutions to diagnose and treat ADHD offenders have also been called for by the probation services, who believe it will help them to support these individuals to avoid potentially breaching their licence or reoffending (Wood, 2024).

At present, public services in the United Kingdom are stretched and have been in need of additional funding for a number of years. With that in mind, naturally, the argument will arise as to the cost of introducing ADHD screening on the scale needed. While I do not have data to estimate this, it could be argued that any potential cost would be significantly less than the potential savings that could be made in managing offending behaviour linked to ADHD through suitable treatment. A report released by the housing charity Shelter in 2010 stated that it costs around £45000 to keep an offender in prison for a year (Shelter England, 2010). Given the high cost of keeping an offender in prison, given the financial burden this places on the criminal justice system, solutions must be found to tackle reoffending. If effective ADHD screening could provide the opportunity for offenders to receive treatment that could reduce ADHD symptoms attributed to offending behaviour, this is something that must be explored.

Once the ADHD offenders have received a diagnosis, treatment options can then start to be explored to help them manage the condition. In the United Kingdom, it is recommended by the National Institute for Clinical Excellence (NICE) that medication be used as a primary treatment for people with severe ADHD (Young and Thome, 2011). Using medication will aim to help reduce ADHD symptoms such as emotional dysregulation and impulsivity. As highlighted in the previous chapter, a study carried out in Sweden found that treating ADHD offenders with medication led to a decrease in criminality of 41 per cent in women and 32 per cent in men (Young *et al.*, 2018). Despite these figures not specifically mentioning violent offending, they do give a positive perspective as the medication aims to reduce emotional dysregulation and impulsivity, which were attributed to the higher levels of violent offending in individuals with ADHD (Young *et al.*, 2011).

Despite the promising figures presented in the Swedish study, it has been suggested that medication, while effective in treating symptoms of ADHD, might not be sufficient when it comes to treating certain serious offenders with ADHD. Supporting these offenders' treatment will need to involve both psychological treatment and the use of medication. This is because these offenders overwhelmingly have additional comorbidities that contribute to the offending behaviour. One example given of a common comorbidity found in ADHD offenders that contributes to the offending behaviour is the high rates of alcohol and substance misuse (Young and Thome, 2011). Supporting these offenders' treatments should aim to utilise a psychological treatment targeting the alcohol or substance misuse, combined with medication to reduce symptoms of ADHD (Young and Thome, 2011).

4.2 Secure Housing Available When Released from Prison

Throughout this dissertation, I've discussed the findings regarding ADHD in relation to the criminal justice system, a large part of which has been in regard to seeing if ADHD screening and treatment can be used to reduce reoffending rates once an offender has been released from prison. While this is important, we cannot ignore the possibility that other factors other than ADHD might be contributing to the offending behaviour once the individual has been released from prison. One such factor is the need for accommodation to be available at the point of release. In 2010, the housing charity Shelter reported that out of the 90,000 people released from prison that year, 30,000 had no accommodation when they were released (Shelter England,2010).

When looking at reducing reoffending, housing is a key element that must be addressed. By ensuring that stable accommodation is available for prisoners upon release will provide them with a foundation to enable those released from prison to engage with support services aimed at reducing offending behaviour. It has been reported that ensuring prisoners have secure accommodation once released can reduce the risk of reoffending by 20 per cent (Shelter England,2010). Addiction has been flagged as a real concern in this regard, with it reported that up to 80 per cent of those released from prison have issues related to addiction. These figures are worrying as Issues related to addiction pose a risk to an individual's ability to remain in stable accommodation (Shelter England,2010). This should be noted as there is an overlap with ADHD offenders who have been found to be at a higher risk of having Issues related to substance misuse (Young and Thome, 2011).

The statistics published by Shelter demonstrate the important impact secure accommodation can make in reducing the risk of reoffending. It could be argued that this could be explained using Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs. Maslow's theory believes that individuals take actions based on their fundamental needs and that until basic needs, including the need for secure accommodation, are met, an individual is unable to work towards future goals (Birch, 1998). When looking to apply this theory in regards to reducing reoffending, by ensuring that individuals have secure accommodation available when they are released from prison, it could help them to engage with support services aimed at reducing offending behaviour, as the individuals' actions will not be based on addressing the basic need in finding secure accommodation. The theory goes on to state that once these basic needs have been met, the individual can pursue what Maslow calls a growth mindset, which is where a person can walk towards goals (Parrish, 2014).

4.3 Implications for Social Work

This has significant implications for social workers. Firstly, the findings that an offender with ADHD appears to make up a disproportionate percentage of the prison population, many of whom are undiagnosed (Young *et al.*, 2018). With this in mind, practitioners must be mindful when working with service users who are involved with the criminal justice system, who might have additional needs that are not being met. In these cases, practitioners must advocate for these service users so they are able to receive appropriate support. This should be done in a collaborative way with the service user, which will promote their wellbeing as outlined in the British Association of Social Workers Code of Ethics (BASW, 2021).

Social work practitioners must also be mindful of the need to support offenders to find stable accommodation, and the impact this could have in reducing the risk of reoffending (Shelter England, 2010). Practitioners must advocate for offenders who are being released with no stable accommodation to ensure that they are treated as a priority need for housing by the local authority, as outlined by the 1996 Housing Act (Housing Act 1996).

While it is acknowledged that housing stock is limited, with 1.29 million households on the waiting list for social housing (Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government, 2024). With this in mind, social work practitioners must work in partnership with housing colleagues to ensure that service users who are released from prison are supported into accommodation effectively.

4.4 Conclusion

This Literature review set out to answer the question: Can the diagnosis and treatment of offenders who have ADHD help to reduce reoffending rates? The findings from the literature consistently highlighted an association between ADHD and higher rates of violent offending and reoffending (Román-Ithier *et al.*, 2017). These higher rates of aggression and violent behaviour found in ADHD offenders are believed to be linked to emotional dysregulation, impulsivity and a low ability to tolerate frustrating situations (Young and Thome, 2011).

Additionally, the findings showed the need to improve the ways in which offenders are screened for ADHD. This is because it is believed that a large proportion of the prison population who are ADHD are undiagnosed and therefore do not receive the support needed (Young *et al.*, 2018). However, once the diagnosis has been obtained, the research has demonstrated some encouraging results. When using

medication to treat symptoms of ADHD offenders in Sweden there was found to be a 41% for women and 32% in men (Young *et al.*, 2018).

While these findings are positive, it has been suggested that a combined psychological and medication treatment is needed to address reoffending. It is believed this combined approach is needed as the offending behaviour is not attributed to ADHD symptoms alone, as these individuals often have a range of different comorbidities that contribute to offending and reoffending (Young and Thome, 2011). This finding in particular goes a long way to answering my research question, but I believe additional research is needed to answer this with more certainty.

4.5 Further Reflections

With this being my first dissertation, the process felt daunting with a lot of unknowns of what to expect. My first challenge was to choose a topic and then refine that topic into my research question. This took a longer time than I had anticipated, which I found to be frustrating at the time. However, I now understand these things take time. Once that was completed, I began searching for literature, which again took far longer than I had anticipated and required a large variety of different searches. This did give me the opportunity to read a number of interesting articles that helped me to gain a greater understanding of the way ADHD impacts people in different settings.

After my articles were selected, I began the process of completing my first draft of the methodology chapter. As this was my first time writing a dissertation, I didn't know how to structure this section and made little progress until I raised this with my supervisor, who helped me to understand how this chapter needed to be written. This was an important lesson for me to ask for help from my supervisor when stuck, rather than waiting until I have something to show them. From that point onwards, I found the experience to be an enjoyable one, although difficult. This was mostly due to the amount of time at placement, meaning the time available to work on my dissertation was limited to weekends. If I were to need to complete a dissertation again in the future, I feel I'd be more confident, as I now understand the process and some of the challenges that can arise.

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